

22	Dandora South East of Nairobi City	ND	ND	ND	6.25	73.96	9.59	40.23	81.94	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	211.97
24	Industrial area east of the Nairobi city centre	9.65	36.97	ND	ND	17.47	25.37	24.1	19.25	132.81	NA	132.81						
25	Industrial area east of the Nairobi city centre	7.08	4.76	ND	ND	12.75	2.86	16.78	19.15	63.38	NA	63.38						
26	Industrial area east of the Nairobi city centre	4.84	39.38	ND	ND	19.75	20.33	29.79	10.2	124.29	NA	124.29						
27	Industrial area east of the Nairobi city centre	5.53	ND	ND	ND	12.8	30.67	35.49	25.26	109.75	NA	109.75						

